

ADOLF HITLER'S RISE TO POWER

Kuchkorov Matkarimkhuja Sirojiddin ugli

Andijan State University, faculty of History, 4th course 11

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8004274>

Annotation: This article covers how Adolf Hitler's childhood became a member of a political party and his rise to power and the beer rebellion of 1923.

Key words: Munich, Reichskansler, Fyurer, "beer revolt"

Adolf Hitler was born on 20 April 1889 in Braunau (Austria), Inna. The future Führer's father, Alois Hitler (1837-1907), had previously been a etiquette, and then worked as a customs officer; because of his illegal birth, he took his mother's surname, shiklgruber, until 1876 (Adolf never took this surname, despite a common opinion). Alois held a non-senior ober-official office. Her mother Klara Pölzl, maiden surname Pelsl, came from a family of workers. At the age of 16, Hitler graduated from a school in Linz, which did not provide a full secondary education. Attempts to enter the Academy of Fine Arts Vienna would be unlucky. After the death of his mother (1908) Hitler moved to Vienna, where he lived in homeless shelters and saw a day for random wages. At that time, he manages to sell a number of his watercolors. Adolf's views were shaped by the influence of the famous anti-Semitic Viennese ober-burgomist, Karl Lueger. He believed that the German nation had greatness and a special mission.

Hitler moved to Munich in May 1913, where he lived his usual life trading watercolours. In the first month of the war, he volunteered for the German army. As a private in France and Belgium, he then served as a yefreytor. As a sending staff of the sixteenth Bavarian Reserve Regiment, it participates in combat operations. Twice injured, he was awarded the Iron Cross II and I class..

The defeat of the German Empire in the war and the November Uprising of 1918 were considered by Hitler to be the act of traitors who "stabbed in the back" the victorious German army.

In late 1918, he returned to Munich and joined the Reichswehr. By order of the command, he was collecting material for the participants in the events of the uprising in Munich. Captain E. Following rem's advice (later a close associate of Hitler), he became part of the "German Workers 'Party" in Munich.

Quickly suppressing its creators from party management, he becomes a full – fledged leader-Führer. On Hitler's initiative, in 1919, the party was renamed-the German National – Social Workers ' Party (NSDAP in German transkipsia). In political publicism, they are called Natsi, as socialists call it Sotsial.

The defeat of the German Empire in the war and the November Uprising of 1918 were considered by Hitler to be the act of traitors who "stabbed in the back" the victorious German army. In late 1918, he returned to Munich and joined the Reichswehr. By order of the command, he was collecting material for the participants in the events of the uprising in

Munich. Captain E. Following rem's advice (later a close associate of Hitler), he became part of the "German Workers 'Party" in Munich.

Quickly suppressing its creators from party management, he becomes a full – fledged leader-Führer. On Hitler's initiative, in 1919, the party was renamed-the German National – Social Workers ' Party (NSDAP in German transkipsia). In political publicism, they are called Natsi, as socialists call it Sotsi

By the early 1920s, the NSDAP would become Bavaria's most prominent right-wing extraterrestrial organization. The assault otrad is headed by Ernst Röhm. Hitler soon becomes a political figure to reckon with. By the end of 1923, the tension in Germany was sharpened. In Bavaria, opponents of parliamentary rule and supporters of the establishment of the dictatorship gather around the Bavarian administration von Carr, with an active role in the coup given to Hitler and his party. On November 8, 1923, Hitler announces the beginning of a national uprising at a rally at Munich's brewery "Byurgerbraukeler" and the overthrow of the Berlin traitor's rule. High Bavarian officials, led by Von Carr, join the proclamation. At night, the otrad of the NSDAP begin to occupy the administrative buildings of Munich. Soon after, however, von Carr and his entourage decide to come to compromise with the center. On November 9, parts of Reichswehr open fire on them as Hitler led his supporters out to Central Square and headed for "Feldgerenhale". Taking the killed and injured, the nationalists and their supporters leave the streets. The history of Germany includes this episode under the name "Beer uprising".

In February-March 1924, the trial of the leaders of the uprising begins. Only Hitler and a few of his supporters sit in the jury chair. The court sentenced Hitler to 5 years in prison, but he was released after 9 months.

The party that lost its leader falls apart. Hitler has to start it all almost from the beginning. He is greatly assisted by Röhm, who begins to restore the assault squads. However, at the rebirth of the NSDAP, Gregor Strasser, the leader of the far-right extremist movements of North and northwest Germany, plays a decisive role. Adding them to the NSDAP ranks, he helped the party to become a nationwide political force from the provincial (Bavarian) level.

At this time Hitler was looking for help at the all-German level. He manages to gain the confidence of the generalitet and establish contact with the industrial magnates. When the parliamentary elections of 1930 and 1932 brought the nationalists a serious increase in MP mandates, in the ruling circles of the state, the NSDAP began to be seen seriously as a participant in political combinations. A move was made to remove Hitler from the party leadership and impose the task on Strasser. Hitler, however, promptly isolates his rival and close friend, depriving him of any influence in the party. It is eventually decided to surround Hitler with Guardians from the traditional conservative parties, giving him the position of chief administrator in the German trenches. On January 31, 1933, President Hindenburg appointed Hitler reichskansler.[2]

Hitler, who was at the top of the reign, demonstrated in the early months that he would not follow any restrictions, regardless of who he came out of. Under the pretext that the burning of the parliament building (Reichstag) was the work of the nationalists, Germany's mass "unification"begins. First the communist and then the Social Democratic parties are banned. A number of parties are forced to disperse themselves. The profsoyuz are eliminated, their property is handed over to the nationalist workers ' front. Opponents of the new government are sent to concentration camps without investigation and trial. The mass

persecution of the "other people" began, and a few years later its culmination would become operation "endlyozung" (final decision), an operation aimed at the physical loss of the entire Jewish people.

Even Hitler's personal (real and potential) opponents from the party and beyond cannot escape repression. On June 30, he personally participates in the destruction of the SA chiefs, who were felt to be not loyal to Führer. The first victim of this loss would be Hitler's previous line-up Röhm. Strasser, von Carr, former reichskansler general Schleicher and other figures are physically lost. Hitler would have absolute government over Germany.

References:

1. M. LAFASOV, U. JO'RAYEV - JAHON TARIXI Akademik litseylar va kasb-hunar kollejlari uchun o'quv qo'llanma. TOSHKENT 2005
2. Shuhrat Ergashev, Begzod Xodjayev, Jamshid Abdullayev - JAHON TARIXI (1918 - 1991-yillar) O'rta ta'lim muassasalarining 10-sinfi va o'rta maxsus, kasb-hunar ta'limi muassasalarining o'quvchilari uchun darslik Birinchi nashr O'zbekiston Respublikasi Xalq ta'limi vazirligi tasdiqlagan Toshkent «TURON-IQBOL» 2017
3. <https://optolov.ru>